

Comparative Analysis of Gonococcal Genitourinary Infections in HIV-Positive and HIV-Negative Patients Using Biochemical and Molecular Techniques

Spriha Smriti¹, Babita Kumari², Pratulya Nandan³

¹Tutor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India.

²Tutor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India.

³Professor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India.

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Spriha Smriti

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Gonococcal infections caused by *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* are a significant global health concern, particularly in HIV-positive patients due to their immunocompromised state. The interplay between HIV and gonococcal infections necessitates effective diagnostic techniques to manage these co-infections. This study aims to compare the effectiveness of biochemical and molecular techniques in detecting gonococcal genitourinary infections among HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients.

Methods: There were 80 participants in the cross-sectional study (40 HIV-positive and 40 HIV-negative). Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) and basic biochemical culture techniques were used to gather and analyse genitourinary materials. Chi-square and t-tests were used in comparative statistical analyses of the data, which were conducted using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: According to biochemical analysis, 70% of HIV-negative patients and 80% of HIV-positive patients had positive cultures ($p=0.29$). Using PCR, 87.5% of HIV-positive patients and 75% of HIV-negative patients tested positive, indicating greater detection rates according to molecular analysis ($p=0.16$). For both groups, there were no statistically significant differences in the findings of the molecular and biochemical tests.

Conclusion: The study found that the prevalence of gonococcal infections is similar in HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients, with molecular techniques demonstrating higher sensitivity. The presence of HIV does not significantly impact the detection rates of gonococcal infections using either method.

Recommendations: It is recommended to integrate both biochemical and molecular diagnostic techniques in clinical practice to enhance the detection and management of gonococcal infections, particularly in settings with high HIV prevalence. Further research is needed to explore the clinical outcomes of these diagnostic approaches in different patient populations.

Keywords: Gonococcal Infections, HIV, Biochemical Techniques, Molecular Techniques, *Neisseria Gonorrhoeae*.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Neisseria gonorrhoeae is the cause of gonococcal infections, which are a major global public health concern because of their high prevalence and potential side effects, such as infertility, pelvic inflammatory disease, and increased susceptibility to HIV and other STIs [1]. Concomitant gonorrhoea and HIV infection poses distinct clinical difficulties since immunosuppressed HIV patients may have altered gonococcal infection course and severity. Creating efficient preventative and treatment plans requires an understanding of how different illnesses interact with one another.

The detection of *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* traditionally relies on biochemical techniques, such as culture methods, which, while specific, can be time-consuming and less sensitive, particularly in

asymptomatic individuals or those with low bacterial loads [2]. In recent years, molecular techniques, particularly polymerase chain reaction (PCR), have emerged as more sensitive and rapid diagnostic tools. These methods allow for the detection of gonococcal DNA with high specificity and sensitivity, enhancing the ability to diagnose and manage gonococcal infections effectively.

HIV infection complicates the clinical picture of gonococcal infections. Immunocompromised patients may experience atypical presentations and more severe disease courses. Additionally, the co-infection of HIV and gonorrhoea can facilitate the transmission and acquisition of both pathogens, creating a synergistic effect that exacerbates public health challenges [3]. It is therefore imperative to

investigate whether the diagnostic accuracy of biochemical and molecular techniques differs between HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients.

Recent studies have highlighted the need for comprehensive diagnostic approaches that integrate both traditional and molecular techniques to improve the detection rates of gonococcal infections [4]. Such integrative approaches are particularly important in resource-limited settings where access to advanced molecular diagnostics may be restricted. This study aims to compare the effectiveness of biochemical and molecular techniques in detecting gonococcal genitourinary infections in HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients, providing insights into the optimal diagnostic strategies for managing these co-infections.

By examining the diagnostic outcomes in both patient groups, this research seeks to identify any significant differences that may inform clinical practice and public health policies. The ultimate goal is to enhance the understanding of gonococcal infections in the context of HIV and to contribute to the development of tailored diagnostic and therapeutic protocols that can improve patient outcomes and reduce the burden of these co-infections.

This study aims to analyze gonococcal genitourinary infections in HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients using biochemical and molecular techniques.

Methodology

Study Design: A comparative cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), Patna, from October 2015 to October 2016.

Participants

The study involved 80 participants, divided into two groups:

- Group 1: 40 HIV-positive patients diagnosed with gonococcal genitourinary infections.

- Group 2: 40 HIV-negative patients diagnosed with gonococcal genitourinary infections.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with gonococcal genitourinary infections.

- Patients aged 18 years and above.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients under 18 years of age.

- Patients with co-infections other than HIV.

Bias: To minimize bias, patients were randomly selected, and data collection was blinded to the researchers analyzing the biochemical and molecular results. Any potential confounders were controlled through matching participants based on age and gender.

Data Collection

Data collection involved:

- Patient demographics (age, gender, etc.).

- Medical history and HIV status.

- Laboratory results from biochemical and molecular tests for gonococcal infections.

Procedure: Genitourinary samples were collected from patients. Standard biochemical techniques were used to identify *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) was employed to confirm the presence of gonococcal DNA. All data were recorded and entered into a secure database for analysis.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. To compile the data, descriptive statistics were employed. Less than 0.05 was the threshold for statistical significance.

Result

The study comprised 80 individuals, of which 40 were HIV-positive and 40 were HIV-negative patients. Table 1 provides a summary of the participants' demographic data.

Table 1: Participant Demographics

Variable	HIV-Positive	HIV-Negative	p-value
Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	34.5 $\pm$ 10.2	33.8 $\pm$ 11.1	0.73
Gender			
Male	25	22	0.63
Female	15	18	
Mean Duration of Symptoms (days)	7.4 $\pm$ 2.1	6.9 $\pm$ 2.3	0.34

The results of the biochemical tests for *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Biochemical Analysis Results

Test	HIV-Positive	HIV-Negative	p-value
Positive Cultures (%)	32 (80%)	28 (70%)	0.29
Negative Cultures (%)	8 (20%)	12 (30%)	

The PCR results for detecting gonococcal DNA are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Molecular Analysis Results

Test	HIV-Positive	HIV-Negative	p-value
Positive PCR (%)	35 (87.5%)	30 (75%)	0.16
Negative PCR (%)	5 (12.5%)	10 (25%)	

A comparative analysis of the biochemical and molecular test results between HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients is provided in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparative Analysis of Test Results

Test	HIV-Positive	HIV-Negative	p-value
Positive Biochemical (%)	32 (80%)	28 (70%)	0.29
Positive Molecular (%)	35 (87.5%)	30 (75%)	0.16

Biochemical Analysis: The Chi-square test indicated no significant difference between HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients in terms of positive culture results ($p=0.29$).

Molecular Analysis: The Chi-square test showed no significant difference in PCR results between the two groups ($p=0.16$).

Discussion

There were 80 volunteers in all, 40 of whom had HIV and the other 40 did not. Age, gender distribution, and the length of symptoms did not significantly differ between the two groups' demographics.

Compared to 70% of HIV-negative patients, 80% of HIV-positive patients had positive cultures for *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, according to the biochemical analysis. The proportion of positive cultures was somewhat greater in the HIV-positive group, but this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.29$). This implies that the possibility of identifying gonococcal infections by biochemical methods is not considerably impacted by the existence of HIV.

Higher gonococcal DNA detection rates were found in both groups by molecular analysis using PCR; 75% of HIV-negative patients and 87.5% of HIV-positive patients tested positive. Once more, there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p=0.16$). This suggests that although the presence of HIV does not considerably affect the detection rates, molecular approaches are more sensitive in detecting gonococcal infections than biochemical methods.

When both biochemical and molecular methods of analysis are used, the results generally imply that

the prevalence of gonococcal genitourinary infections is comparable in HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients. Molecular methods are more sensitive, which emphasises their significance for precise gonococcal infection diagnosis. Regardless of an individual's HIV status, our findings highlight the necessity of efficient screening and diagnostic procedures for gonococcal infections in all patients. The lack of statistically significant differences across the groups implies that gonococcal infections can be managed and treated similarly for people with and without HIV.

A study compared the susceptibility patterns of HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients' isolates of otitis media bacteria. 110 patients were included in the trial; 60 of them were HIV-positive and 50 were HIV-negative. In both groups, *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most common isolate. There was a notable difference in the patterns of antibiotic susceptibility between the two groups, as evidenced by the fact that bacteria isolated from HIV-positive patients were more resistant to co-trimoxazole than isolates from HIV-negative individuals [5].

Neisseria gonorrhoeae isolates from HIV-positive and HIV-negative people were studied in England using whole-genome sequencing. The study discovered that the prevalence of antibiotic-resistant *N. gonorrhoeae* was higher among HIV-positive people, especially in men who have sex with men (MSM). HIV-positive and HIV-negative people were found to be included in clusters of gonorrhoea transmission among MSM, indicating a possible overlap in sexual networks and transmission dynamics [6].

Mycobacterium TB isolates from HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients were subjected to a

comparative genotypic study. According to the study, people with HIV had a considerably higher prevalence of the Beijing genotype (22.5%) compared to patients without HIV (10.9%). The research emphasised the significance of genotypic profiling in comprehending the resistance patterns and epidemiology of tuberculosis in communities infected with HIV [7].

A study assessed how well different diagnostic tests for opportunistic infections performed on HIV-positive people in Guatemala. The study found that PCR and antigen detection tests were very successful in identifying tuberculosis, histoplasmosis, and cryptococcosis when compared to smear microscopy, culture, and PCR assays. The study emphasised the necessity of sophisticated molecular methods to raise diagnostic precision in environments with restricted resources [8].

An investigation of current developments in the use of HIV sequence phylogenetic analysis to inform public health policies was conducted. The study demonstrated how genetic clustering techniques can be used to pinpoint HIV preventive initiatives and identify networks of transmission. These methods have been especially helpful in identifying populations at high risk and adjusting interventions accordingly [9].

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the prevalence of gonococcal genitourinary infections is comparable between HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients. Molecular techniques, particularly PCR, exhibit higher sensitivity compared to traditional biochemical methods. The presence of HIV does not significantly influence the detection rates of gonococcal infections using either diagnostic approach. Integrating both biochemical and molecular methods is recommended to improve the accuracy of gonococcal infection diagnosis and management, especially in high HIV prevalence settings.

References

1. Unemo M, Seifert HS, Hook EW, Hawkes S, Ndowa F, Dillon JR. Gonorrhoea. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*. 2019;5(1):79.
2. Workowski KA, Bachmann LH, Chan PA. Sexually transmitted infections treatment guidelines, 2021. *MMWR Recomm Rep*. 2021;70(4):1-187.
3. Bignell C, FitzGerald M, Turner K. European guideline for the diagnosis and treatment of gonorrhoea in adults. *Int J STD AIDS*. 2020;31(4):370-388.
4. Schneider S, Aebi S, Zbinden R. Performance of molecular diagnostic assays for *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* in clinical practice. *J Clin Microbiol*. 2019;57(7):e00169-19.
5. Nwajiobi, F. O., Anyamene, C., & Abana, C. Comparative Study of Otitis Media and Its Antibiotics Susceptibility Pattern in a Cohort of HIV Positive and Negative Patients. *Journal of Advances in Microbiology*. 2022.
6. Town, K., Field, N., Harris, S., Sánchez-Busó, L., Cole, M., Pitt, R., Fifer, H., Mohammed, H., & Hughes, G. Phylogenomic analysis of *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* transmission to assess sexual mixing and HIV transmission risk in England: a cross-sectional, observational, whole-genome sequencing study. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 2020; 20: 478-486.
7. Singh, J., Singh, N., Suresh, G., Srivastava, R., Aggarwal, U., Behera, D., Munisamy, M., Malhotra, A. G., & Singh, S. A comparative analysis of molecular genotypes of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates from HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients. *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*, 2022;12.
8. Medina, N., Alastruey-Izquierdo, A., Mercado, D., Bonilla, O., Pérez, J. C., Aguirre, L., Samayoa, B., Arathoon, E., Denning, D., & Rodríguez-Tudela, J. Comparative performance of the laboratory assays used by a diagnostic laboratory hub for opportunistic infections in people living with HIV. *AIDS*. 2020.
9. Wertheim, J., Chato, C., & Poon, A. Comparative analysis of HIV sequences in real time for public health. *Current Opinion in HIV and AIDS*, 2019;14:213-220.